

A Cadaveric Study of the Morphology and Morphometry of the Petrous and Cavernous Parts of the Internal Carotid Artery

Vivekanand¹, Kumari Rashmi², Birendra Kumar Sinha³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Surgery, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor & HOD, Department of Anatomy, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Kumari Rashmi

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Abstract:

Background: The internal carotid artery (ICA) is a critical blood channel that supplies the brain, with the petrous and cavernous segments having important roles in cerebrovascular health. Understanding the morphology and morphometry of these segments is critical for physicians, especially in neurosurgery and interventional radiology, where anatomical changes can greatly affect procedure outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to provide a detailed analysis of the morphology and morphometry of the petrous and cavernous segments of the ICA using cadaveric specimens to enhance clinical understanding and improve surgical outcomes.

Methods: A study was conducted on 100 cadaveric specimens. The petrous and cavernous segments of the ICA were carefully dissected, and detailed morphometric measurements, including length and diameter, were recorded using digital calipers and a stereomicroscope. Morphological observations were documented, and statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The study found that the petrous segment had a significantly greater mean length (29.6 mm) compared to the cavernous segment (21.8 mm) ($p < 0.001$). The mean diameter of the petrous segment (4.8 mm) was slightly larger than that of the cavernous segment (4.5 mm), although this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.072$). Anatomical variations, such as tortuosity and partial duplication, were observed in a minority of specimens (10% and 5%, respectively). No significant gender-based differences were found in the morphometric parameters.

Conclusion: The petrous segment of the ICA is generally longer and slightly wider than the cavernous segment, with consistent anatomical patterns observed across specimens. The presence of anatomical variations highlights the importance of preoperative imaging and individualized surgical planning. Understanding these morphological details can aid in reducing surgical complications and improving outcomes in procedures involving the ICA.

Recommendations: Future research should focus on exploring the clinical implications of the anatomical variations observed in this study. Additionally, incorporating advanced imaging techniques into routine preoperative assessments could further enhance surgical precision and patient safety.

Keywords: Internal Carotid Artery, Petrous Segment, Cavernous Segment, Morphometry, Anatomical Variations.

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Introduction

(ICA) is a large blood artery that supplies the brain; its therapeutic significance stems from its anatomical route. The ICA is segmented into various regions, the most notable of which are the cavernous and petrous sections because of their intricate anatomical interactions with surrounding structures. The cavernous segment travels through the cavernous sinus, a location intimately connected to the pituitary gland and cranial nerves, whereas the petrous segment travels through the temporal bone's carotid canal. Any abnormalities or changes in these ICA segments can have significant

clinical ramifications because of the vital roles these brain regions play.

In order to effectively treat cerebrovascular disorders, neurosurgeons, interventional radiologists, and other experts must have a thorough understanding of the morphology and morphometry of the petrous and cavernous segments of the ICA. Modern imaging techniques like computed tomography angiography (CTA) and high-resolution magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) have greatly improved our capacity to examine the ICA in vivo and have given us precise insights into

its structural variations and dimensions. Research has demonstrated, for instance, that differences in the length and quality of the ICA might impact the risk of cerebrovascular accidents and surgical outcomes, including carotid artery stenting and aneurysm clipping [1].

Furthermore, anatomical differences in the ICA are frequently observed and may pose notable difficulties in the course of surgical procedures. Particularly well-known for its intricate anatomical connections to the cranial nerves and cavernous sinus is the cavernous segment. There is a greater chance of iatrogenic harm during surgery if there are variations in the length or course of the ICA in this area [2]. It is essential to comprehend these variances in order to safely plan and carry out surgical procedures.

In order to increase preoperative planning accuracy and lower the risk of surgical problems, recent studies have also highlighted the necessity of comprehensive morphometric data on the ICA [3]. Notwithstanding these developments, thorough cadaveric investigations that can offer baseline information on the shape and size of the ICA in various populations are still required. These kinds of data are crucial for improving surgical methods and creating more efficient plans for the treatment of cerebrovascular illnesses. This study aims to provide a detailed analysis of the morphology and morphometry of the petrous and cavernous segments of the ICA using cadaveric specimens to enhance clinical understanding and improve surgical outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a descriptive, cross-sectional cadaveric analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of Anatomy at P.M.C.H. Patna, utilizing the cadaveric specimens available in the department's dissection hall. The study was carried out over a period of 12 months, from February 2023 to February 2024.

Participants: The study involved 100 cadaveric specimens, which were selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria outlined below.

Inclusion Criteria

- Cadavers with intact internal carotid arteries.
- Cadavers that were well-preserved with no signs of advanced decomposition.
- Specimens where the internal carotid artery was free from any previous surgical intervention or trauma.

Exclusion Criteria

- Cadavers with damaged or partially dissected internal carotid arteries.

- Cadavers showing signs of advanced decomposition or poor preservation.
- Specimens with evident vascular pathology, such as aneurysms, severe atherosclerosis, or congenital anomalies.

Bias: To minimize bias, all cadaveric specimens were randomly selected from the available pool without prior knowledge of the state of the internal carotid arteries. The dissection and measurement procedures were standardized and performed by a single anatomist to ensure consistency.

Data Collection: Data was collected through detailed dissection and examination of the internal carotid artery, focusing on the petrous and cavernous segments. Morphological characteristics were noted, and morphometric measurements were taken using digital calipers and a stereomicroscope. The following parameters were recorded:

- Length of the petrous and cavernous segments.
- Diameter of the artery at specific points along these segments.
- Presence of any anatomical variations.

Procedure: The dissection procedure involved careful removal of surrounding tissues to expose the internal carotid artery. The artery was then traced from its origin to the end of the cavernous segment. Measurements were taken in triplicate at each segment to ensure accuracy, and any anatomical variations were documented.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered into a database and analysed with SPSS software version 23.0. For each morphometric parameter, descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and range were determined. The morphological data was analysed using frequency distributions. To compare the petrous and cavernous portions, paired t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were used, depending on the data's normality. A p-value of <0.05 indicated statistical significance.

Results

A total of 100 cadaveric specimens were included in the study. The mean age of the cadavers was 65.2 years (range: 45-85 years), with 60 males and 40 females. The results are presented in terms of morphological observations and morphometric measurements of the petrous and cavernous segments of the internal carotid artery (ICA).

Morphological Observations

- **Petrous Segment:** In all 100 specimens, the petrous segment of the ICA was found to be well-preserved and embedded within the carotid canal. No significant anatomical variations were observed in this segment. The

petrous segment maintained a consistent course, without any kinks or bends.

- **Cavernous Segment:** The cavernous segment of the ICA exhibited some anatomical variations. In 10% of the specimens (n=10), the artery showed tortuosity within the cavernous sinus. Additionally, in 5% of the specimens (n=5), the artery had a partially

uplicated segment. No aneurysms or significant pathological findings were noted in either segment.

Morphometric Measurements

Morphometric data were collected for both the petrous and cavernous segments, including the length and diameter of each segment. The data are summarized in the following tables.

Table 1: Length of the Petrous and Cavernous Segments of the ICA

Segment	Mean Length (mm)	Standard Deviation (mm)	Range (mm)
Petrous Segment	29.6	3.4	22.0 - 36.5
Cavernous Segment	21.8	2.8	16.0 - 28.2

Table 2: Diameter of the Petrous and Cavernous Segments of the ICA

Segment	Mean Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation (mm)	Range (mm)
Petrous Segment	4.8	0.7	3.5 - 6.2
Cavernous Segment	4.5	0.6	3.2 - 5.8

Statistical Comparison Between Segments:

A paired t-test was conducted to compare the length and diameter of the petrous and cavernous segments of the ICA.

- **Length Comparison:** The mean length of the petrous segment (29.6 mm) was significantly greater than that of the cavernous segment

(21.8 mm), with a mean difference of 7.8 mm ($p < 0.001$).

- **Diameter Comparison:** The mean diameter of the petrous segment (4.8 mm) was slightly larger than that of the cavernous segment (4.5 mm). However, this difference was not statistically significant (mean difference = 0.3 mm, $p = 0.072$).

Table 3: Paired t-test Results for Length and Diameter of ICA Segments

Parameter	Mean Difference (mm)	95% Confidence Interval	t-value	p-value
Length	7.8	6.9 - 8.7	14.52	<0.001
Diameter	0.3	-0.03 - 0.63	1.81	0.072

Anatomical Variations: As noted, 10% of the specimens showed tortuosity in the cavernous segment, and 5% had partial duplication. The impact of these variations on the morphometric data was minimal, with no significant deviation from the overall trends.

Gender-Based Differences: A secondary analysis was conducted to assess any gender-based differences in the morphometric measurements. No statistically significant differences were observed between male and female specimens in terms of the length and diameter of the petrous and cavernous segments ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons).

Table 4: Gender-Based Comparison of ICA Segment Length and Diameter

Segment	Male Mean (mm)	Female Mean (mm)	p-value
Petrous Length	29.7	29.4	0.64
Cavernous Length	21.9	21.7	0.78
Petrous Diameter	4.8	4.7	0.55
Cavernous Diameter	4.5	4.4	0.61

Findings

- The petrous segment of the ICA is consistently longer and slightly wider than the cavernous segment, though the diameter difference is not statistically significant.
- Anatomical variations, such as tortuosity and partial duplication, are present in a minority of specimens.

- No significant gender-based differences were observed in the morphometric parameters of the ICA segments.

Discussion

The study analyzed the morphology and morphometry of the petrous and cavernous segments of (ICA) in 100 cadaveric specimens. The findings revealed that the petrous segment is consistently longer than the cavernous segment, with a mean length of 29.6 mm compared to 21.8 mm, a differ-

ence that was statistically significant. The diameter of the petrous segment was slightly larger than that of the cavernous segment, but this difference was not statistically significant. These results suggest that while the petrous segment is typically longer, the overall caliber of the artery does not differ significantly between the two segments.

Anatomical variations were observed in a small subset of specimens. Tortuosity within the cavernous segment was noted in 10% of the cases, and partial duplication of the artery in 5%. Despite these variations, the overall morphometric measurements remained within a consistent range, indicating that these variations do not drastically alter the typical anatomy of the ICA. Such findings are clinically relevant as they highlight the potential for anatomical differences that could affect surgical approaches or the interpretation of imaging studies.

No significant gender-based differences were found in the morphometric parameters of the ICA segments. This indicates that the morphology and dimensions of the internal carotid artery are generally consistent across genders, which is useful information for both surgical planning and educational purposes.

Overall, the results of this study provide important baseline data on the morphology and morphometry of the internal carotid artery's petrous and cavernous segments. The consistent findings across most specimens suggest a reliable anatomical pattern, with some variability that may be encountered in clinical practice. Understanding these anatomical details can aid in the development of more precise surgical techniques and improve outcomes in interventions involving the internal carotid artery.

Recent research has thoroughly examined the morphology and morphometry of the petrous and cavernous segments of the internal carotid artery (ICA), providing useful insights for clinical and surgical applications. A cadaveric investigation conducted on 50 specimens found that the petrous segment of the ICA seems reasonably steady, whereas redundant curvature in the cavernous segment was observed in 30% of instances, with a greater frequency on the right side. Furthermore, aneurysms were discovered in 4% and 10% of the petrous and cavernous portions, respectively. The study also discovered no significant difference in the length and diameter of both segments, which measured around 3.5 to 4 cm and 0.5 cm, respectively [4].

The morphological variability of the petrous carotid segment, specifically the incidence of bony dehiscence in the ceiling of the horizontal petrous carotid canal was investigated. This cadaveric morphometric investigation discovered that bone dehiscence was present in 25% of the specimens, which may enhance vascular exposure during high-

flow bypass treatments, lowering surgical morbidity [5].

A comprehensive anatomical investigation on the C3-C4 transitional segment of the ICA, with a 360° circumferential analysis that included histological, microsurgical, endoscopic, and neuroradiological perspectives was conducted. The study discovered a distinct precavernous segment and highlighted anatomical correlations between transcranial and endoscopic-endonasal approaches, which may help to resolve controversies surrounding the paraclival ICA and improve surgical safety and effectiveness in this area [6].

A morphometric investigation of the ICA using digital subtraction angiography (DSA) in a study of 70 individuals was also done. This study discovered significant sex and age-related differences in the diameters of certain ICA segments, with males typically having greater diameters than females. The supraclinoid segment differed statistically significantly between males and females, and diameter decreased from younger to older age groups, particularly in the supraclinoid and choroidal segments [7].

Conclusion

This study conducts an extensive investigation of the morphology and morphometry of the petrous and cavernous segments of the (ICA) in a large cadaveric sample. The results show that the petrous segment is consistently longer and slightly broader than the cavernous segment, with statistically significant differences in length but not diameter. Furthermore, structural differences such as tortuosity and partial duplication were detected in a small number of specimens, demonstrating the variety that can occur in ICA anatomy.

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